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Optimizing Planting Density To Enhance Sustainable Sugarcane Production

Abdul Khaliq (Corresponding author)

Oilseeds Research Institute, AARI, Faisalabad Email: khaliq1775@gmail.com

Ishfaq Rasul

Department of Plant Protection, Ministry of National Food Security & Research,
Government of Pakistan

Zaheer Sikandar

Oilseeds Research Institute, AARI, Faisalabad

Muhammad Shafique

Sugarcane Research Institute, Faisalabad

Mubashra Yain

Sugarcane Research Institute, Faisalabad

Salma Niaz

Sugarcane Research Institute, Faisalabad

Abdul Majeed

Agricultural Biotechnology Research Institute AARI Faisalabad

Amina Rashid

Department of Agronomy, University of Agriculture, Faisalabad

Muneeba

Department of Agronomy, University of Agriculture, Faisalabad

Babar Hussain Babar

Sugarcane Research Institute, Faisalabad

Ansar Mehmood

Agriculture Department, Jadeed Group of Companies

Muhammad Arif

Agronomic Research Institute, AARI, Faisalabad

Muhammad Abdullah Butt (Corresponding Author)

Department of Food Science, Government college University Faisalabad

Email: muhammadabdullahbuttfst@gmail.com

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Ahsan Mubarak

Sugarcane Research Institute, AARI, Faisalabad

ABSTRACT

Graphical Abstract

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High cost of production is the main constrain in the adoption of sustainable sugarcane production. Huge quantity of seed contributes about 20% to cost of production. Therefore, optimization of rational seed rate with respect to genotypes is need of time. General recommendation for all genotypes and varieties is not a rational approach as it wastes the seed resources. Site specific varieties and variety specific production technology is the only one solution to cope challenge of climate change in agriculture. The scientist has to re-think about the current general recommendation of production technology in all field crops. In this view, a field experiment was conducted during the spring season 2021 at the Sugarcane Research Institute, Faisalabad, to determine variety specific seed rate for promising sugarcane clones viz. S2008-S2008-AUS-133, S2005-US-54, and CPF-253 and three different seed rates viz. 35,000, 50,000, 65,000 three-budded setts (TBS) per hectare. The study was laid out in a randomized complete block design with a split-plot arrangement and three replications. The results indicated that the sugarcane variety CPF-253 performed best at a seed rate of 50,000 TBS per hectare, producing 118,000 millable canes per hectare, a cane yield of 123.90 t/ha, and a sugar yield of 16.67 t/ha. The sugarcane clone S2008-S2008-AUS-133 achieved its best performance at the highest seed rate of 65,000 TBS per hectare,

yielding 120,080 millable canes per hectare, a cane yield of 120.08 t/ha and a sugar yield of 15.19 t/ha. The highest 114,880 millable canes per hectare, maximum a cane yield of 105.69 t/ha, and highest sugar yield of 13.77 t/ha in sugarcane clone S2005-US-54 at 50,000 TBS per hectare. These findings suggest that optimal seed rate is variety-specific. It is therefore apparent that adjustment in population to match the genetic potential of each variety can result in maximum cane and sugar yields.

Keywords: Sugarcane, Variety-Specific Seed Rate, Three-Budded Setts, Sugar Yield, Cost Of Production

Introduction

Plant population is one of the most important agronomic factors affecting final yield and quality in sugarcane (Khaliq et al., 2021). Optimal plant density is vital for maximum biomass production through the efficient use of available resources like sunlight, water, and nutrients (Zhao et al., 2022). A low plant population may cause underutilization of land and other means, which may reduce yield (Dumont, et al., 2019). Very high plant density, on the other hand, creates high inter-plant competition for the acquisition of vital resources such as light, water, and nutrients (Gadallah, et al., 2020). This often leads to thinner and weaker stalks, reduced millable canes (Gadallah, et al., 2019), and overall, reduced cane and sugar yields (Galal, et al., 2018). Sugarcane is a highly sensitive crop to the initial planting density, and for that, the final yield is almost dependent on the number of millable canes per unit area (Prabhakar et al. 2014). The planting density sets the initial stalk population, and it thereby affects the interspace competition for resources, such as light, water, and other nutrients, which is also responsible for tillering and the final survival of the stalks (Ijaz et al., 2023; Nadeem et al., 2018).

Recent studies continue to confirm that yield optimization depends on finding the economic and agronomic optimum planting density. Although some studies have indicated that high-density planting can result in rapid canopy closure with a possibility of improving yield, other findings showed that high-density planting may or may not produce more cane or sugar yield compared to low-density planting because of the plant's strong compensatory capacity to manipulate stalk number and individual stalk weight. A compensatory mechanism is central to high variability in results across different regions (Amin et al., 2023; Butt et al., 2025a, Khaliq et al., 2021). In addition, low-density planting systems have been investigated, and though the lowest densities can realize higher initial productivity in plant cane, the ratoon crops often present a drastic reduction in yield, closely associated with a lower number of stalks per meter. This questions long-term sustainability and requires careful evaluation over successive cultivation cycles (Nazeer et al., 2024; Afghan et al. 2022). The influence of seed rate on the performance of sugarcane has been studied in numerous research works. Experiments usually show that increasing the density of planting significantly increases the number of initial shoots and millable canes per unit area. However, a common drawback is that the effect of increased plant density is often manifested through an adverse relationship with individual stalk weight. With increased density, individual stalks tend to be lighter and thinner. Finding the optimal balance in seed rate is therefore quite important for optimization

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of both number and weight of the cane for maximum yield.

Furthermore, the response of different planting densities is highly dependent on sugarcane cultivar type. Genetic variations in tillering ability (Abu et al. 2020), growth habit, including erect and lodging, and general vigor lead to different optimal plant populations among varieties (Sohaib et al., 2023; Lan et al. 2023). A few varieties may produce prolific tillering to compensate for a low seed rate (Zhao et al. 2022), while others need a high initial population for full yield expression (Chand et al., 2011). For example, past studies on S2008-S2008-AUS-133 clones have reported a favorable response to higher planting densities, recording a greater number of millable canes and tonnage of cane. However, the optimal sowing density for varieties CPF-253 and S2005-US-54 under agro-climatic conditions remains scanty. Therefore, the performance evaluation of these promising clones under various seed rates will establish variety-specific recommendations for optimal attainment of plant stands and maximum productivity.

However, this efficacy of any particular planting density is not universal but instead is influenced profoundly by the genetic composition of the variety. Varieties of sugarcane differ substantially in their tillering capacity, stalk diameter, stalk height, and tolerance to stress (Zhao et al. 2022). This immediately creates a Variety and Planting Density interaction-an effect that is often reported in recent literature. Some research on new clones under various planting geometries reported that while the general effect of spacing on sugar yield may be non-significant, individual clones showed significant variation in yield potential and specific optimum planting geometry. Other research has illustrated categorically that variety performance in terms of tillering and final millable cane population is influenced by planting geometry and planting date, thus signaling the need for a varietal management prescription in order to maximize the productivity of newly released varieties (Khaliq et al., 2024). This concept indicates that the optimum planting rate is not a general recommendation but rather varietal-specific in nature to maximize the genetic potential of a cultivar (Birhanie et al., 2020; Butt et al., 2025c).

The ultimate yield of sugar per hectare is a product of cane yield and juice quality, both of which are strongly affected by population density. Maximizing millable cane population remains the single most important determinant of final cane yield. Afghan et al. (2024) confirm that while high planting density can maximize cane and sugar productivity, economic viability often stands at an intermediate or even lower density due to such costs as planting material, one of the main cultivation expenses (Belay et al., 2023). This study, therefore, under the prevailing conditions, considers the interaction of three distinct seed rates with three promising new varieties to estimate variety-specific population targets for optimizing millable cane production and economic sugar yield in the Faisalabad environment. By doing so, established principles will be translated into practical, localized, and cost-effective recommendations.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This study was conducted during the 2021 spring season at the Sugarcane Research Institute, Faisalabad, to identify the optimal seeding density for three promising sugarcane clones, V_1 : S2008-AUS-133, V_2 :S2005-US-54, and V_3 : CPF-253. The trial

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followed a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with a split-plot arrangement, replicated three times. Experimental treatments involved three seeding rates S_1 : 35,000, S_2 :50,000, and S_3 : 65,000 three-budded setts (TBS) per hectare-with sub-plots measuring 4 m x 8.4 m. The TBS were manually positioned in furrows according to the designated density for each plot. All experimental units received uniform agronomic management, including standardized irrigation, fertilization, and pest control. Irrigation water quality affects soil CO₂ emissions and crop performance, influencing sustainable sugarcane production under different planting densities (Shakeel et al., 2021). Baseline soil physicochemical properties were assessed prior to sowing according to AOAC (2005) protocols (Table 1). The crop reached physiological maturity and was harvested in December. Yield components and quality parameters were then documented following the methodologies established by Chand et al. (2011), Butt et al. (2024) and Meade and Chen (1977), respectively.

Table 1. Soil physico-chemical Analysis of the experimental site

Soil properties	Physico-chemical Analysis report
Sand (%)	51
Silt (%)	20
Clay (%)	29
Textural class	Sandy clay loam
Organic matter (%)	0.89
Available nitrogen (%)	0.45
Available phosphorus (mg kg ⁻¹)	19.60
Extractable potassium (mg kg ⁻¹)	149
Moisture (%)	34
Bulk density (g cm ⁻³)	1.96
Ph	7.89

Climatic variables for the experimental site were sourced from the Meteorological Observatory within the Crop Physiology Section at AARI, Faisalabad, and are illustrated in Figure 1. The crop received a standardized nutrient application of 168-112-112 kg NPK ha⁻¹, utilizing Urea (46% N), Di-ammonium Phosphate (18% N, 46% P₂O₅), and Sulphate of Potash (60% K₂O). The entire phosphorus and potash requirements, along with one-third of the total nitrogen, were applied as a basal dose during sowing (Ahmed et al., 2023; Rashid et al., 2026). The remaining nitrogen was top-dressed in two equal splits: the first at the completion of germination (45 days post-planting) and the second during the tillering stage (90 days post-planting). Irrigation was scheduled according to the crop's water requirements. Manual harvesting was conducted on December 15, 2021, followed by the recording of primary yield components and Commercial Cane Sugar (CCS) levels using standard protocols. Statistical analysis was performed through ANOVA as described by Panse and Sukhatme (1954), Ahmed et al. (2024), Khan et al. (2024) and Steel et al. (1997). Furthermore, genetic parameters-including genotypic and phenotypic variances, their respective coefficients, broad-sense heritability, and genetic advance (as a percentage of the mean)-were calculated following established methodologies.

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Fig. 1 The meteorological data of the research area. The data was obtained from the Meteorological Observatory, Crop Physiology Section, AARI, Faisalabad, Pakistan.

Results and Discussion:

Sugarcane agronomic and yield traits:

The effects of three different seed rates (35,000, 50,000, and 65,000 TBS/ha) on the performance of three sugarcane varieties (CPF-253, S2008-AUS-133, and S2005-US-54) are presented in the figure 2,3. The analysis revealed significant variations among the treatments for all recorded parameters. The highest germination percentage (Fig.2) was observed in variety CPF-253 at a seed rate of 50,000 TBS/ha (50.33%), which was statistically superior to most other treatments. Variety S2005-US-54 also showed high germination (49.67%) at the same seed rate. The lowest germination was recorded for S2008-AUS-133 at 35,000 TBS/ha (41.00%).

Variety S2005-US-54 exhibited the highest tillering capacity (Fig.2), producing a maximum of 1.77 tillers per plant at the 50,000 TBS/ha seed rate. This was statistically equal to its performance at 65,000 TBS/ha (1.52 tillers) and that of S2008-AUS-133 at 65,000 TBS/ha (1.48 tillers). Variety CPF-253 showed the lowest tillering capacity across all seed rates, reaching a maximum of only 1.16 tillers per plant. The number of millable canes (Fig.3) was significantly influenced by the interaction between variety and seed rate. For variety S2008-AUS-133, the highest number of millable canes (120,080/ha) was achieved at the highest seed rate of 65,000 TBS/ha. In contrast, varieties CPF-253 and S2005-US-54 produced their maximum number of millable canes (118,000/ha and 114,880/ha, respectively) at the medium seed rate of 50,000 TBS/ha. The lowest seed rate of 35,000 TBS/ha resulted in a significantly lower number of millable canes for all varieties.

Cane yield (Fig.3) followed a similar trend to millable canes. Variety CPF-253 produced the highest cane yield (123.90 t/ha) at the 50,000 TBS/ha seed rate. Variety S2008-AUS-133 also performed strongly, yielding 120.08 t/ha at the 65,000 TBS/ha seed rate. These two treatments were statistically superior to most others. The lowest cane yields were recorded for all three varieties at the 35,000 TBS/ha seed rate, ranging from 79.66 to 91.23 t/ha.

Figure 2: Interactive effect of different seed rates on germination percentage and tillers per plant in different sugarcane genotypes.

Where: V₁: S2008-AUS-133, V₂:S2005-US-54, and V₃: CPF-253. S₁: 35,000, S₂:50,000, and S₃: 65,000 three-budded setts (TBS) per hectare

Figure 3: Interactive effect of different seed rates on number of millable canes (000/ha) and cane yield (t/ha) in different sugarcane genotypes.

Where: V₁: S2008-AUS-133, V₂:S2005-US-54, and V₃: CPF-253. S₁: 35,000, S₂:50,000, and S₃: 65,000 three-budded setts (TBS) per hectare

Sugarcane quality traits:

The CCS% showed less variation compared to yield parameters (Fig.4). Variety CPF-253 maintained a high and stable CCS% across all seed rates (13.32-13.45%). Variety S2005-US-54 also recorded a high CCS% (13.47%) at the 65,000 TBS/ha rate.

Variety S2008-AUS-133 generally has a lower CCS% compared to the other two varieties, with its lowest value being 12.08%. The ultimate measure of performance, sugar yield (Fig.4), was maximized in variety CPF-253 at the 50,000 TBS/ha seed rate, achieving an exceptional 16.67 t/ha. This was statistically the highest yield. The next best performance was from S2008-AUS-133 at 65,000 TBS/ha (15.19 t/ha) and CPF-253 at 65,000 TBS/ha (15.06 t/ha). Variety S2005-US-54 reached its peak at 50,000 TBS/ha with a sugar yield of 13.77 t/ha. In all three varieties represented in this field study, the lowest seed rate produced the lowest sugar yield.

Figure 4: Interactive effect of different seed rates on CCS (%) and sugar yield (t/ha) in different sugarcane genotypes.

Where: V₁: S2008-AUS-133, V₂:S2005-US-54, and V₃: CPF-253. S₁: 35,000, S₂:50,000, and S₃: 65,000 three-budded setts (TBS) per hectare

Correlation Matrix:

The correlation matrix presents the association between different key traits of spring-sown sugarcane, namely Germination Percentage (GP), Tillers per plant (TPP), Millable Cane (MC), Cane Yield (CY), Sugar Yield (SY), and Commercial Cane Sugar (CCS) in Fig. 5. A strong positive association was recorded between GP and TPP at $p \leq 0.01$ level of significance, indicating that increased seed setts germination enhances the number of tillers produced per plant. The TPP also showed a significant positive association with MC at $p \leq 0.01$ level of probability, thereby indicating that increased tillering results in more number of millable stalks. MC showed strong positive association with CY and SY at $p \leq 0.01$ level of significance, indicating increase in millable cane directly enhances cane yield and hence sugar yield. The positive association between CY and SY at $p \leq 0.01$ level of probability confirms that more biomass production is positively linked with the enhanced sugar production. The latter is a primary requirement for enhancing the overall productivity of sugarcane. Association of SY with CCS, and other agronomic traits mentioned above indicated the importance of sugar yield as an economically important trait for determining

commercial cane sugar contents. Thereafter, SY showed significant positive association with CCS at $p \leq 0.01$ level of probability, indicating enhancement in sugar yield directly enhances commercial sugar recovery from cane. The matrix indicated that GP exerts its indirect influence on CCS through TPP, MC, CY, and SY, thus forming a cascading improvement path from seed germination to final sugar output. These findings suggest that breeding programs must emphasize selection for high GP and TPP to evoke synergistic improvements in millable cane, cane yield, sugar yield, and commercial sugar contents, thereby optimizing both the productivity and profitability of spring-sown sugarcane systems.

Figure 5: Correlation matrix between various yield and quality traits in spring sown sugarcane.

Where GP is germination percentage, TPP is tillers per plant, MC is millable cane, CY is cane yield, SY is sugar yield, CCS% is commercial cane sugar. These results clearly indicated that variety and plant population interact strongly, ruling out the appropriateness of the use of a 'one-size-fits-all' seed rate. Indeed, the optimum seed rate depends on the genetic characteristics of a variety, especially those related to tillering capacity. For all varieties, the lowest seed rate, this was 35,000 TBS/ha, consistently gave the poorest performance for all yield-related parameters because the low plant population in the early stages of growth was insufficient to produce the required number of millable canes necessary to result in a high yield even after tillering. Increasing the seed rate from 35,000 to 50,000 or 65,000 TBS/ha raised the millable canes significantly-the main driver of cane yield, which in turn directly translated into drastic increases in both cane and sugar yield. The three varieties reacted differently to increasing rates of seeding. CPF-253 performed the best at the medium seed rate of 50,000 TBS/ha. At this density, it gave the maximum cane and sugar yield in the entire experiment. However, further increase in density to 65,000

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TBS/ha showed a slight, though non-significant reduction in yield. This indicates that beyond 50,000 TBS/ha, the intraspecific competition for resources like light, water, and nutrients may start adversely affecting stalk weight or development, thereby negating the effect of increased cane population.

S2008-AUS-133, with its relatively lower tillering capacity, needed the highest seed rate of 65,000 TBS/ha to realize its maximum yield. At lower densities, it was unable to throw sufficient numbers of canes to be competitive. Its performance represents a classic example of a variety that relies upon a high initial plant population rather than prolific tillering in achieving its yield potential. S2005-US-54 exhibited the greatest tillering capacity and, as with CPF-253, it also favored the medium seed rate of 50,000 TBS/ha for optimal performance. In this, its high tillering capacity was sufficient to populate the space available. The yield at the highest rate of 65,000 TBS/ha did not increase further, which once more suggests that competition became a limiting factor for this high-tillering variety.

These findings emphasize the need for plant population synchronization with the particular growth habit of the variety (Sajjad et al., 2025; Butt et al., 2025b). Varieties with low tillering, such as S2008-AUS-133, require higher seed rates to compensate for lower shoots per plant. For varieties with moderate to high tillering, the best balance at an intermediate seed rate would allow plants to express their tillering potential without suffering from excessive competition, which may cause a reduction in stalk girth and weight, as was observed in CPF-253 and S2005-US-54.

It's evident in the findings that there's a distinct and very significant interaction between which varieties or clones of sugarcane you plant and how densely you plant them. This corresponds with traditional agricultural research that considers genotype-by-environment interactions as essential in optimizing the right plant density. It's interesting to see that CPF-253 and S2005-US-54 both maximize their potential at the 50,000 tiller-bearing sets per hectare plant density, indicating that both varieties can handle or even grow well in moderate plant densities. They appear able to till harder or distribute their resources effectively, able to still maximize the production of millable cane even at non-optimal plant densities. This non-optimal plant density appears to be the sweet spot between minimizing intra-specific competition and maximizing light and nutrient availability, thus maximizing the production of millable cane and consequently cane and sugar. On the other hand, the performance of the clone S2008-S2008-AUS-133 varied, reaching its top yield production at the highest seeding rate tested, 65,000 TBS/ha. This tends to indicate that either the plant has less aptitude for tillering or simply that the plant performs better when the canopy is more densely packed. At this higher density, however, there is a need to compensate for any mortality or loss in tillering to have sufficient millable canes per unit area (approximately 120,080 canes per ha). The additional competition in the denser plantings did not impact the yield adversely, which is an indication that the plant has high aptitude for high plant density, a desirable characteristic for a production plantation where competition is effectively addressed.

Finally, for sugarcane, the objective is to produce every hectare with as much sugar as possible. The results clearly indicate that optimal sugar productiveness can only be achieved through optimizing the seed rate. The most effective combination, that of CPF-253 with a seed rate of 50,000 TBS/ha, produced 16.67 tons of sugar per hectare,

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much higher than what could be produced through other, less optimal, combinations. The fact that the number of millable stalks exerts a highly significant influence on cane and subsequently sugar produce has important practical implications-it is always desirable to decrease an effective seed rate, if permissible, to lower production costs.

Conclusion:

The evidence finds strong support for adapting the protocols for planting densities according to the variety. Such variations between the optimal densities necessitate local research studies that address the refinement in crop management for new sugarcane varieties. Follow-up research could examine the possible biological mechanisms underpinning these varietal responses regarding densities, for instance, the regulation of tillers, photo conversion efficiency, or stalk diameter.

The optimum seed rate resulting in the highest production of cane and sugar is variety-specific.

For the variety CPF-253, the recommended seed rate is 50,000 TBS/ha, as this density produced the highest cane yield (123.90 t/ha) and sugar yield (16.67 t/ha).

For the variety S2008-S2008-AUS-133, the recommended seed rate is 65,000 TBS/ha. This higher density is required for this specific clone to achieve its maximum potential, yielding 120.08 t/ha of cane and 15.19 t/ha of sugar.

For the variety S2005-US-54, the recommended seed rate is 50,000 TBS/ha, which optimized the balance between its high tillering capacity and plant population to produce the best yields (105.69 t/ha cane and 13.77 t/ha sugar).

A seed rate of 35,000 TBS/ha is sub-optimal for all tested varieties and leads to significant yield losses.

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CONFLICT OF INTERESTS Authors declare no conflict of interest.

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References

- Abu-Ellail, F. F., Gadallah, A. F. I., & El-Gamal, I. S. H. (2020). Genetic variance and performance of five sugarcane varieties for physiological, yield and quality traits influenced by various harvest age. *Journal of Plant Production*, 11(5), 429-438.
- Afghan, S., Arshad, W. R., Khan, M. E., & Malik, K. B. (2022). Sugarcane breeding in Pakistan. *Sugar Tech*, 24(1), 232-242.

Online ISSN

3007-3197

Print ISSN

3007-3189

<http://amresearchreview.com/index.php/Journal/about>

- Afghan, S., Khan, M. E., Verma, K. K., & Nikpay, A. (2024). Economic importance and yield potential of sugarcane in Pakistan. In *Sugarcane Cultivation and Management* (pp. 263-291). Apple Academic Press.
- Ahmed, F., Waris, F., ibni Zamir, S., Sajjad, M., Nazeer, S., Khan, A., & Mustafa, F. (2023). Response of Different Organic and Inorganic Fertilizers on Alfalfa Yield Under Different Types of Irrigation Water. *Haya Saudi J Life Sci*, 8(1), 1-8.
- Ahmed, N., Saeed, M., Asghar, A., Abdullah Butt, M., Afzaal, M., Saeed, F., ... & Teferi Asres, D. (2024). Utilization of *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* as probiotic adjunct culture for the development of tempeh. *International Journal of Food Properties*, 27(1), 1279-1289.
- Amin, H., Habib, A., Asif, M., Hameed, M. U., Wassi, M., Manzoor, M., ... & Sajjad, M. (2023). Effect of Foliar Application of Boron, Zinc and Manganese on Growth, Yield and Oil Contents of Sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.). *Asian J. Soil Sci. Plant Nutri*, 9(4), 86-94.
- AOAC. (2005). *Official Methods of Analysis*. 26th Ed. Association of Official Analytical Chemists, Washington, DC, USA.
- Belay, T., Gedebo, A., & Tena, E. (2023). Variability, heritability and genetic advance in sugarcane (*Saccharum* spp. hybrid) genotypes. *Cogent Food Agric*. 9(1): 1–16.
- Birhanie, N., Legesse, H., & Jalata, Z. (2020). Effect of blended fertilizer and levels of Phosphorus on Yield and Juice Quality of Sugarcane at Fincha Sugar Estate, Ethiopia. *International Journal of Photochemistry and Photobiology*, 10(1), 21-29.
- BUTT, M. A., ARSHAD, M. U., IMRAN, A., & AFZAAL, M. (2025a). NUTRITIONAL AND BIOSAFETY ASSESSMENT OF A NOVEL SOY-WHEY HYBRID PROTEIN CROSSLINKED BY MICROBIAL TRANSGLUTAMINASE IN SPRAGUE DAWLEY RATS. *TPM–Testing, Psychometrics, Methodology in Applied Psychology*, 32(S7 (2025): Posted 10 October), 597-608.
- BUTT, M. A., ARSHAD, M. U., TASLEEM, S., IMRAN, A., & AFZAAL, M. (2025c). COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF CHICKEN AND MEAT ANALOGUE PATTIES: EVALUATING PHYSICO-CHEMICAL, COOKING, TEXTURAL, MICROBIAL, AND SENSORY ATTRIBUTES. *TPM–Testing, Psychometrics, Methodology in Applied Psychology*, 32(S6 (2025c): Posted 15 September), 1274-1285.
- Butt, M. A., Shahzad, M. H., Tasleem, S., Riaz, R., Ye, X., Khalid, B., ... & Arshad, M. U. (2025b). Design of a Sustainable Whey–Corn Hybrid Protein Powder for Enhanced Nutrition, Functionality, and Environmental Stewardship. *Innovative Research in Applied, Biological and Chemical Sciences*, 3(2), 32-51.
- Butt, M. A., Shukat, R., Afzaal, M., Saeed, F., Imran, A., Ahmed, A., ... & Shah, M. A. (2024). Comparative evaluation of the quality and safety attributes of local and branded beef seekh kabab. *Cogent Food & Agriculture*, 10(1), 2360769.

Online ISSN

3007-3197

Print ISSN

3007-3189

<http://amresearchreview.com/index.php/Journal/about>

- Chand, M., Khippal, A., Singh, S., Lal, R., & Singh, R. (2011). Effect of planting material and seed rate in pit planted sugarcane (*Saccharum* spp. hybrid complex) in sub-tropical India. *Indian Journal of Agronomy*, 56(1), 78-82.
- Dumont, T., Thong-Chane, A., Barau, L., Siegmund, B., & Hoarau, J. Y. (2019). Genetic variabilities and genetic gains for yield components in regional sugarcane breeding programmes on Réunion Island. *Sugar Tech*, 21(6), 868-878.
- Gadallah, A. F. I., & Abd El-Aziz, R. M. (2019). Effect of row spacing and nitrogen fertilization on yield and quality of some sugarcane varieties. *Journal of Biological Chemistry and Environmental Sciences*, 14(1), 215-233.
- Gadallah, A. F. I., Ebid, M. H. M. & Makhlof, B. S. I. (2020). Crop assessment, phenotypic correlation and stability of new sugarcane genotypes under different seed rates. *Journal of Plant Production* 11(6): 531–539.
- Galal, M. O. A., Osman, M. A. M. & Ali, A. M. K. (2018). Evaluation of some promising sugarcane varieties for yield, quality and natural infection with Pokka Bong disease under different row spacing. *Egyptian Journal of Agricultural Research*, 3(9): 1–13.
- Ijaz, B., Waraich, E. A., Shah, A., & Nazeer, S. (2023). Morpho-physiological responses of wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) to foliar applied potassium under different planting geometry. *Journal of Global Innovations in Agricultural Sciences*, 11(1), 27-33.
- Khaliq, A., Ahmad, N., Ahmad, H. B., Younus, M., Saeed, S., & Hussain, I. (2021). Optimizing seed rates and effects of direct and indirect selection indices in sugarcane crop. *Indian Journal of Agricultural Research*, 55(2), 235-238.
- Khaliq, A., Ahmed, H. B., Ahmed, N., Majeed, A., Arif, M., Saher, A., & ul Sher, R. (2024). Comparative Evaluation of Sugarcane Genotypes for Adaptability Studies in the Agro-ecologies of Sargodha, Punjab, Pakistan: Comparative Studies of Sugarcane Genotypes. *Biological Sciences-PJSIR*, 67(1), 80-85.
- Khan, W. A., Inam-ur-Raheem, M., Rasheed, H., Butt, M. A., Saeed, F., Afzaal, M., ... & Hailu, G. G. (2024). Comparative effect of olive oil and flaxseed oil on drug induced hepatotoxicity in rats. *Food Science & Nutrition*, 12(11), 9673-9681.
- Lan, Y., Xu, B., Huan, Y., Guo, J., Liu, X., Han, J., & Li, K. (2023). Food security and land use under sustainable development goals: Insights from food supply to demand side and limited arable land in China. *Foods*, 12(22), 4168.
- Meade, G. P., & Chen, J. C. (1977). *Cane Sugar Handbook*. A Wiley-Interscience Publication. New York, USA.
- Nadeem, M., Maqsood, M., Ehsanullah S., & Ahmad, N. (2018). Need to identify ideal planting density aiming not only for productivity gains but also for efficient use of available resources. *Int. J. Plant Prod.* 12(3): 419–431.
- Nazeer, S., Sajjad, M., Ahmad, T., Idrees, M., Ali, A., Khurshid, M. A., ... & Khaliq, A. (2024). Effect of micronutrients (zinc, iron and boron) application on the yield and quality of late sown wheat. *Plant Health*, 3(1), 41-47.
- Negi, A., & Koujalagi, D. (2018). Study of genetic variability, heritability and genetic advance for various yield and quality traits in sugarcane genotypes

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- (*Saccharum officinarum*). *International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences*, 7(4), 1464-1472.
- Panase, V. G., & Sukhatme, P. V. (1954). Statistical methods for agricultural workers. ICAR, New Delhi, India.
- Prabhakar, K., Sagar, G. K., Chari, M. S., Reddy, C., & Sekhar, S. C. (2014). Effect of planting geometry and nitrogen application through fertigation on production and quality of sugarcane. *Agricultural Science Digest-A Research Journal*, 34(3), 223-225.
- Rashid, M. S., Gull, Z., Butt, M. A., Hayat, S., Azam, S. E., Saeed, S., ... & Umar, N. (2026). The Role of Functional Probiotic Yogurt Consumption in Medical Weight Loss: A GLP-1 Friendly Nutritional Approach to Metabolic Health in UK Adults: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19121209>. *Pakistan Journal of Medical & Cardiological Review*, 5(1), 1623-1632.
- Sajjad, M., Ijaz, B., Khil, A., Ibtahaj, I., Hur, M., Azizi, N., ... & Babar, S. (2025). Influence of different organic mulches on growth, yield and oil content of maize (*Zea mays* L.) hybrids and soil physical properties. *Journal of Ecological Engineering*, 26(11).
- Shakeel, A., Anjum, L., Ibni Zamir, S., Rizwan, M., Arshad, M., Mehmood, Q., ... & Waqas, A. (2021). Irrigation water quality effects on CO₂ emissions along with crop and soil responses. *Pakistan Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 58(2), 637-642.
- Singh, K., Singh, K., & Kumar, S. (2016). Effects of seed rate, sett size and seed treatment on spring planted sugarcane. *Journal of Sugarcane Research*, 3(1).
- Sohaib, N., Arif, M., Shah, M. N., Mahmood, S., Ali, H., Amjid, M., ... & Anwar, H. (2023). Exploring the Role of Anti-Oxidant on Growth and Yield of Cotton to Mitigate the Heat Stress.
- Steel, R. G. D., Torrie J. H. & Dickey D. A. (1997). *Principles and Procedures of Statistics: A Biometrical Approach*. 3rd Ed. McGraw-Hill Book Co., New York, USA.
- Zhao, Y., Liu, J., Huang, H., Zan, F., Zhao, P., Zhao, J., ... & Wu, C. (2022). Genetic improvement of sugarcane (*Saccharum* spp.) contributed to high sucrose content in China based on an analysis of newly developed varieties. *Agriculture*, 12(11), 1789.